

Introduction

SEPTEMBER marked the 22nd anniversary of the attack on the World Trade Centre on September 11, 2001. Today, as back then, the EU's geopolitical role in world security is at stake. Admittedly, much has changed since 9/11, especially as great-power competition retook centre stage. However, one pressing question from the early 2000s remains actual: is the EU *geopolitically and geo-economically* fit for these times? This article is devoted to the underexplored role that wealth redistribution and solidarity within the EU play in answering this question.

A Brief History of the EU's Ineffective Geo-economic Policies

In the early 2000s, optimists saw the tragic attack on the World Trade Centre as an opportunity to expand the European Union's security infrastructure. Indeed, EU institutions "systematically invoked" terrorism to justify the launch or expansion of "a broad set of risk-management programmes".² However, these efforts have derailed due to both intra-EU and geopolitical factors. In part, US imperial excesses in the Middle East, supported by the UK, divided EU member states

along East/West lines.³ However, more importantly, the EU remained unequipped for dealing with these new threats due to the lack of its own law-enforcement and defence forces that were dependent on national command centres.⁴

However, the real legacy of that experience is much more far-reaching than mere dependence on a mightier ally. In fact, George W. Bush's ensuing "War on Terror" changed the playbook of international relations forever. Sanctions became the preferred way to deal with all types of foreign enemies: from hostile powers to terrorist organisations smuggling oil.⁵ Thus, with its tight economic integration and impressive wealth, the EU could have turned into a key global security player.

Yet, the opposite happened. Since 9/11, the EU's financial warfare has been either a copy of US policies or an embarrassing failure.⁶ Especially after the 2008 Great Recession, and the ensuing political upheavals, the EU's ability to influence geopolitical events faltered. Crucially, this weakness did not simply reduce the EU's ability to establish its own geo-economic and strategic autonomy *vis-à-vis* the US. Rather, it impaired power projection in the EU's immediate neighbourhood⁷

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2 Alexandra Gheciu, *Securing Civilization? The EU, NATO and the OSCE in the Post-9/11 World* (Oxford University Press, 2008), 39.

3 Ekaterina Balabanova, "Media and Foreign Policy in Central and Eastern Europe Post 9/11: In from the Cold?," *Media, War & Conflict* 4, no. 1 (2011): 69–82.

4 Doron Zimmermann, "The European Union and Post-9/11 Counterterrorism: A Reappraisal," *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism* 29, no. 2 (2006): 123–145, 123.

5 Juan Carlos Zarate, *Treasury's War: The Unleashing of a New Era of Financial Warfare*, First Edition (New York: PublicAffairs, 2013).

6 Miroslav N. Jovanović, "Economic Sanctions: Disappointing Old Wine in New Bottles," *Economia Internazionale / International Economics* 75, no. 4 (2022): 545–76.

7 Ritsa Panagiotou, "The Greek Crisis as a Crisis of EU Enlargement: How Will the Western Balkans Be Affected?," *Southeast European and Black Sea Studies* 13, no. 1 (2013): 89–104.

and emboldened potentially adversarial superpowers like Russia.⁸

The EU's Geo-economics Challenges for the 2020s: Raw Materials, Foreign Investments, and Chips

EU member states have been unwilling to set up a working regime to jointly deal with geo-economic challenges until now. Hence, the Union has failed to unshackle itself from a minor role in the latest game of geopolitics: *supply chains*. Though, the 2020s seem to be serving a good hand to the EU. In fact, an already unruly relationship with Moscow turned into declarations that European countries were “already at war with Russia”.⁹ Meanwhile, a formerly working relationship with Beijing is transforming into explicit strategic competition and geo-economic rivalry.¹⁰

The EU's stance on Russia and China reflects and accommodates the US's revamped focus on great-power competition. As a matter of fact, EU institutions have initiated more geo-economic regulations since the Trump administration began antagonising China than in the previous two decades. These efforts have led to the passing of the Regulation on Foreign Direct Investment Screening, the Critical Raw Materials Act, and the Chips Act. This mushrooming new geo-economic legislation suggests that EU and national officers see a window of opportunity. Otherwise said, geo-economic competition may help Brussels achieve the superpower status it failed to achieve in the 2000s.

However, these efforts will fail if no lesson is learnt from past failures. In order to be effective, the EU's new geo-economics should follow two guiding principles. First, these policies should not give foreign actors any opportunity to weaken the member states' resolve to act together. Else, the EU risks reliving 2003, when the US prevented the formation of a unified European front against the Second Gulf War. Second, geo-economic success is contingent on domestic stability –both political and economic. But burning bridges with Russia basically overnight and doing the same, just more gradually, with China threatens both. After all, the fact that the EU attempts to portray de-risking as a “non-confrontational”¹¹ stance does not make it necessarily true. Indeed, de-risking is essentially a buzzword with no clear meaning, and, “unless policymakers clarify what that term does and does not mean, it could do more harm than good”,¹² because, from a Chinese perspective, it is simply “decoupling done slower”.¹³

Analysing the Relation between Wealth and Support for Ukraine

Economic status is not a factor often considered in the reproduction of geopolitical divides within the EU. Nevertheless, an analysis of public opinion on EU-Russia relations indicates that wealth inequalities within the Union may be playing a significant role.

- 8 Andrew Foxall, “From Evropa to Gayropa: A Critical Geopolitics of the European Union as Seen from Russia,” *Geopolitics* 24, no. 1 (2019): 174–93.
- 9 Elena Teslova, “Russia Calls on Germany to Clarify Berlin's Status in Moscow-Kyiv War,” *Anadolu Ajansı*, January 29, 2023, <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/russia-ukraine-war/russia-calls-on-germany-to-clarify-berlins-status-in-moscow-kyiv-war/2798859>.
- 10 Balázs Gargya, “China is a partner, competitor and rival,” *EU Watch*, October 31, 2022, <https://www.euwatch.be/china-is-a-partner-competitor-and-rival-to-the-eu/>.
- 11 Agathe Demarais, “What Does ‘De-Risking’ Actually Mean?,” *Foreign Policy*, August 23, 2023, <https://foreignpolicy.com/2023/08/23/derisking-us-china-biden-decoupling-technology-supply-chains-semiconductors-chips-ira-trade>.
- 12 Carl Bildt, “The Risks of ‘De-Risking,’” *Project Syndicate*, June 20, 2023, <https://www.project-syndicate.org/commentary/us-europe-china-de-risking-problematic-buzzword-by-carl-bildt-2023-06>.
- 13 Wang Yufan, “Decoupling vs. De-Risking,” *China-US Focus*, June 27, 2023, <https://www.chinausfocus.com/foreign-policy/decoupling-vs-de-risking>.

At least, this is what a regression analysis of the available data suggests. Namely, using a generalised additive model (GAM) with the regression equation $Y = \alpha + f_1(PPP) + f_2(X) + \varepsilon$. Where PPP stands for Purchasing Power Parities (i.e., relative wealth levels),¹⁴ Y is support for Ukraine according to Eurobarometer data,¹⁵ α is the intercept of the model, f_1 and f_2 are polynomials, X is a control variable, and ε are the regression errors. The control variables test whether the relation between PPP and Y is robust to factors such as the distance between a country's capital and Kyiv, membership of the Soviet Bloc during the Cold War, and Putin's approval rating. In all cases, the relation between relative wealth levels and support for Ukraine is highly significant ($p < 0.05$ significance), and none of the controls are significant ($p > 0.1$ significance). Finally,

given that the errors are not normally distributed, the best goodness-of-fit measure is the adjusted R^2 , which ranges from 0.2997 to 0.3323. Thus, approximately 30% of the variability in support for Ukraine corresponds to changes in PPP, regardless of distance from Kyiv, historical legacies, and approval of Putin.

Most simply, these results are visible juxtaposing the maps showing the share of respondents looking positively at the EU's support for Ukraine and PPP (Figure 1). There are several plausible explanations for such findings relying, for instance, on Inglehart's theory on post-material values.¹⁶ However, the most pressing issue is not why such differences exist but rather, how to manage them to ensure the EU can conduct a coordinated and effective foreign policy.

Figure 1. On the right, The Percentage of Respondents by Country Who Approve of the EU's Help to Ukraine According to the Eurobarometer.¹⁷ On the left, Purchasing Power Parities in the EU as Estimated by Eurostat.¹⁸

14 Eurostat, "Purchasing power parities (EU27_2020=1)," Eurostat data, September 29, 2023, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/product/view/prc_ppp_ind?lang=en.
 15 As reported in Rene Rabeder, "EU survey: Who wants to continue supporting Ukraine - Austria in 21st place," Exxpress, February 21, 2023, <https://exxpress.at/eu-umfrage-wer-die-ukraine-weiter-unterstuetzen-will-oesterreich-auf-platz-21/>.
 16 Ronald Inglehart, "The Silent Revolution in Europe: Intergenerational Change in Post-Industrial Societies," *American Political Science Review* 65 (1975): 991-1017.

On Route to Missing Another Chance: How the Regulation on Foreign Direct Investment Screening and the Chips Act Threaten Member States' Resolve to Unity

In light of these facts, the EU is undermining itself by refusing to engage with existing inequalities amongst member states in its geo-economic rethinking. Particularly as external analysts keep evoking the risk that geo-economics competition may exacerbate economic disparities within the Union.

For example, "poorer EU countries risk being left behind"¹⁹ when it comes to the distribution of the Chips Act's subsidies. Meanwhile, more affluent countries are already reaping the benefits: STM, the

largest European contract manufacturer and semiconductor designer, is set to construct a €5.7 billion facility in France,²⁰ and the American chip giant Intel plans to invest €17 billion in Germany.²¹

Similarly, the EU has introduced more stringent regulations regarding foreign investments in member states, particularly in the high-tech sector. The origins of this initiative can be traced back to a 2019 white paper addressing concerns about potential distortions caused by foreign mergers and acquisitions (M&A) in the Single Market.²² The objective was to mitigate the risk of hostile third countries gaining undue influence on EU firms, potentially acquiring their intellectual property, or impeding competitors' growth through unfair competition.²³

Figure 2. The Restrictions on Chinese M&A Activity Fuelled a Rise in Chinese Venture Capital Investment (Right Figure) that Benefits Mainly Already-wealthy Countries (Left).²⁶

17 Rabeder, *EU survey: Who wants to continue supporting Ukraine - Austria in 21st place.*

18 Eurostat, Purchasing power parities (EU27_2020=1).

19 Alicia Garcia-Herrero and Nicolas Poitiers, "Europe's Promised Semiconductor Subsidies Need to Be Better Targeted," Bruegel, October 17, 2022, <https://www.bruegel.org/blog-post/europes-promised-semiconductor-subsidies-need-be-better-targeted>.

20 Nic Fleming, "How Grenoble Has Mastered Industry-Academia Science Collaborations," *Nature*, January 19, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-00109-x>.

21 Intel, "Intel in Germany," Intel Corporation, March 15, 2022, <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/corporate-responsibility/intel-in-germany.html>.

22 Directorate-General for Competition (European Commission), "White Paper on Levelling the Playing Field as Regards Foreign Subsidies," (COM/2020/253 final, June 17, 2020), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=COM:2020:253:FIN>.

23 Tilman Kuhn, Orion Berg, Marc Israel, and Kate Kelliher, "The EU Releases Its Second Annual FDI Report Showing Increased Momentum in FDI Regulation and Screening in the EU27," White & Case LLP, September 7, 2022, <https://www.whitecase.com/insight-alert/eu-releases-its-second-annual-fdi-report-showing-increased-momentum-fdi-regulation>.

However, the resulting legislation led to two undesirable outcomes.²⁴

Firstly, it restricted an already limited flow of high-tech foreign direct investment (FDI) into the EU's periphery, originating mostly from China. Secondly, it enabled wealthier member states to safeguard their national champions from foreign takeovers and competition, while directing much-needed foreign capital toward non-M&A investments in the most advanced economies. Empirical data supports this interpretation (Figure 2), as the regulation incentivised foreign investors to shift away from M&A activities to grant venture capital to tech start-ups, primarily in Germany and France. Consequently, the majority of incoming FDIs in strategic and high-tech sectors is concentrated in the EU's most advanced economies, rather than in those more in need of it.²⁵ Moreover, it seems that de-risking is not eliciting positive reactions from Beijing. Rather, as the EU toughens its stance, China seems to actively strengthen its partnership with the UK –which can deviate freely from EU rules after Brexit.

Key Guiding Principles to Correct the Route

EU authorities are wasting another chance at asserting their role as a key global player, although the international order's fluidity would seem to be the ideal environment for a more assertive EU. Brussels is failing at leveraging wealth, its main (if not only) geopolitical strength, to the member states' collective benefit. Just like in the early 2000s, the EU is ignoring the persistent gap in interests and needs amongst member states and seeding future division. Hungary's manoeuvres in pursuit of its national interests should be a harbinger of what is to come.

Fortunately for the EU, high-stake geo-economics is in its infancy. Hence, there still is time to change course and run a tight ship. Yet, doing so would require transforming the current conceptual framework by embedding geo-economic competition. Rather than relying blindly on supposedly 'fair' market forces, the EU should take on a more dirigiste role. Instead of depriving the national capitals of their already scarce prerogatives, Brussels should foster coordination and recognise national specificities. These apparently abstract ideas can be translated into extremely concrete and pragmatic funding schemes and industrial policies.

More Pragmatic Funding Schemes

For instance, this means that a comprehensive geo-economic policy agenda should be established at the Union level, emphasising broader cooperation. Furthermore, existing funding schemes should be expanded to finance research and development (R&D) policy. Practically, this could underpin a Union-wide semiconductor research initiative to reduce dependence on China and the US. In particular, public involvement would be necessary to focus R&D on issues that fall beyond the purview of the private sector, such as fundamental/theoretical research and prototype development. Coherently, it may be beneficial to allocate funds to participating countries in a manner that is both meritocratic (anticipated contributions to the final outcome, comparative advantages in the relevant domain) and solidary (prioritise projects that assign substantial implementation responsibilities to lower-income countries with demonstrated expertise).

24 Regulation (EU) 2022/2560 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on foreign subsidies distorting the internal market, PE/46/2022/REV/1, OJ L 330, December 23, 2022, 1–45.

25 Agatha Kratz, Max J. Zenglein, Gregor Sebastian, and Mark Witzke, "Chinese FDI in Europe: 2021 Update: Investments Remain on Downward Trajectory – Focus on Venture Capital," Mercator Institute for China Studies (MERICS), 27 April 2022, 3, <https://merics.org/sites/default/files/2022-04/MERICS-Rhodium-Group-COFDI-Update-2022-2.pdf>.

26 Inglehart, The Silent Revolution in Europe: Intergenerational Change in Post-Industrial Societies.

Industrial Policy

As industrial policy makes a comeback, the EU must recognise that increased governmental interventions are not just desirable, but also necessary to compensate for reduced investments from rival countries like China. As history has shown, the European Union can create exceptions to its founding treaties to facilitate more direct state intervention in the markets. Thus, Brussels can relax state-subsidy rules to allow state-sponsored takeovers and investments in critical sectors. Such operations should be implemented in such a way as to guarantee that the wealthy EU member states do not benefit from them disproportionately, more than the other member states. Other developed economies have already adopted this approach. For instance, the Japanese Investment Corporation, a fund supported by Tokyo, is acquiring the semiconductor giant JSR for over six billion euros. The underlying objective is clear: the Japanese government intends to strengthen its competitive edge in materials crucial to the manufacture of semiconductors at all costs.²⁷

In addition, Brussels should aim at creating the preconditions for continued joint action by reducing inequalities and fostering stability. For example, the EU could implement harmonised workforce training programmes to mitigate spatial inequalities, while also allocating supplementary funds for the roll-out at a national level of free professionalisation courses in microelectronics. These courses would equip the workforce in de-industrialising peripheral countries with the skills required to work in semiconductor manufacturing and other crucial high-tech sectors. Importantly, the disbursement of these funds should be contingent on demonstrating that access to these courses is designed to ensure equal opportunities and address disparities within the EU.

Conclusion: As Only the Fittest Survive, the EU Should Get Its Hands Dirty

Exactly 22 years ago, 9/11 unleashed a new era of geo-economic confrontation centering around economic sanctions and financial warfare. At the time, the EU could have taken advantage of the situation and established itself as a key global actor. But, a combination of the US's external influence and internal weaknesses prevented this leap forward. In the years after the War on Terror, the EU was embroiled in numerous domestic and international crises. As a result, member states' resolve to act jointly in matters of geopolitics waned. Overall, the 2000s and 2010s taught that European unity requires economic and political stability to fend off third parties' interference.

Nowadays, the US's pivot to Asia and antagonistic stance *vis-à-vis* China and Russia offer the EU another shot at the top. In an era of great-power competition, the EU is trying to strengthen its geo-economic policy tools. But apparently, bureaucrats and policymakers are prone to commit the same mistakes that followed 9/11. The Regulation on Foreign Direct Investment Screening, the Critical Raw Materials Act, and the Chips Act are weakening European unity by entrenching existing cleavages amongst member states. As a result, the resolve to coordinate effectively when it comes to geo-economic confrontation with Russia and China will remain feeble. Moreover, national interests will grow increasingly divergent over the coming decades as inequalities worsen.

Learning from the errors of the past and correcting the course is still possible. And it requires little more than a hands-on approach that swaps economic ideology for pragmatism. Whether Brussels is ready for this change remains unclear. Meanwhile, foreign actors rub their hands with satisfaction.

²⁷ Arjun Kharpal, "Japan-Backed Fund to Buy Critical Semiconductor Firm JSR for \$6.3 Billion as Chip Tensions Rise," CNBC, June 26, 2023, <https://www.cnbc.com/2023/06/26/japan-backed-fund-to-buy-semiconductor-firm-jsr-for-6point3-billion.html>.